

Impact of Local and Landscape Factors on Spotted Wing Drosophila Epidemiology

Summary report of work conducted in 2025-2026.

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Summary

Monitoring of Spotted Wing Drosophila (SWD) abundance at the James Hutton Institute over a twelve-year period (2013-2025) has shown that insect numbers were low until 2020. In 2021, numbers started to increase, and this increase was sustained in 2022, 2023 and 2025, although numbers dropped off in 2024. In most cases, the numbers caught per trap per week were 10-100 fold lower than those reported for other areas of the UK. The SWD monitoring data collected at the institute is being analysed to understand the role of meteorological conditions and habitat composition on annual variation in insect abundance.

Background

The Spotted Wing Drosophila (SWD), *Drosophila suzukii*, is an invasive fruit fly which originated in Japan and has since spread across the world, first being detected in the UK in 2012. In the UK, SWD is a pest of soft and stone fruit, laying eggs in ripening and ripe fruit of many plant species. If left uncontrolled, SWD infestation can result in extensive financial losses for the grower.

Methods

SWD has been monitored in Scotland for thirteen years (2013-2025) at the James Hutton Institute in Dundee, following an established protocol (AHDB, 2022). Modified Droso traps with Cha-Landolt bait were positioned in and around fruit crops and checked for SWD every 1-2 weeks in the summer and every 2-4 weeks in the winter months. Ten traps were used during 2013-2021, and five traps in 2022-2025. The number of female and male SWD adults was recorded in each sample and expressed as an average number per trap per week by averaging the trap catch over the preceding sampling period (i.e. between 1 and 4 weeks). No data are shown for 2013 as no SWD were detected in the traps.

Results

In all years, the number of SWD caught at JHI (**Fig. 1**) remained very low until week 29 when an increase in numbers was observed. During the years 2014-2020, the numbers remained low (<5 individuals per trap per week) for the rest of the year. Since 2021, there was a sharp increase in the number of SWD caught from week 33 onwards and numbers remained high until week 47. Figure 2a shows the largest recorded peak weekly value of SWD per trap caught at JHI, which was low throughout 2014-2020, but increased in 2021 onwards. The peak weekly value in 2024 was, however, lower than the values recorded in 2022 and 2023, and closer to the value recorded in 2021.

The peak value in 2025 at the end of August was the highest that had been recorded at JHI (**Fig.2a**). This peak occurred earlier than peaks in previous years. The peaks that occurred later in the season were similar or slightly lower than those seen in 2023 at that time in the year.

It was not possible to compare overall abundance (total SWD catch) at this site for each of the twelve monitoring years, because the number of traps used in the monitoring varies between the different years. However, it is possible to compare the total catch for weeks 25-52 in 2022-2025 when same 5 traps were used over the same monitoring period (**Fig. 2b**). The results show that the increase in catch size recorded in 2022 and 2023, which was still much lower than the catches recorded in southern UK, was not sustained in 2024 but continued to increase in 2025.

The increase in SWD abundance at the Hutton experimental site in 2025 was noted and to verify if this trend occurred at other sites, monitoring traps were established at commercial farms where historical data were available for comparison. Monitoring took place from 7th October 2025 to the 6th of January 2026 and therefore the data from August and September 2025, when the highest SWD abundance at the JHI experimental site occurred was not captured. The trap catches are currently being analysed and counted.

Future work

A modelling approach is being used to explore the causal drivers of annual variability in SWD abundance in relation to meteorological conditions and habitat conditions (Skelsey et al., 2025).

Fig 1. The mean number of SWD per trap per week detected at the James Hutton Institute. Values for 2014 – 2021 are means of 10 traps, while values for 2022-2025 are the mean of 5 traps.

Fig 2a. The peak value of the mean number of SWD per trap per week caught at the James Hutton Institute in the period 2014 – 2025.

Fig 2b. The total number of SWD caught in 5 traps weeks 25 to 52 at the James Hutton Institute in 2022-2025

Acknowledgements

The Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board and Scottish Government funded the SWD monitoring in Scotland from April 2014 to March 2022. SWD monitoring is currently supported by the Scottish Government’s Strategic Research Programme (2022-2027) funded by the Rural & Environment Science & Analytical Services Division.

References

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Skelsey, P., Zuta, A., Brandt, J., Malloch, G., Mitchell, C and Karley, AJ. Impact of local and Landscape Factors on Spotted Wing Drosophila Epidemiology – summary of report of modelling work conducted in 2025. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15752940

Citation

Please cite this report as: Malloch, Mitchell, Smith, Brandt, Dempster & Karley. 2026. Impact of Local and Landscape Factors on Spotted Wing Drosophila Epidemiology - Summary report of work conducted in 2025-2026. Research report for RESAS project JHI-A1-1: WP4: Impact of Local and Landscape Factors on Spotted Wing Drosophila Epidemiology. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18743842